

BUILDING NAVIGABLE LISTENING EXPERIENCES BASED ON SPATIAL SOUNDFIELD CAPTURE: THE CASE OF THE ORCHESTRE SYMPHONIQUE DE MONTRÉAL PLAYING BEETHOVEN’S SYMPHONY NO. 6

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ABSTRACT

We present our work towards the recording and reproduction of a captured soundfield as a virtual walking experience. In this context, we propose a methodology for recording symphonic concerts that captures both stage and concert hall listening perspectives. The recreation of the experience allows for a virtual walker to explore a plurality of listening perspectives in the venue, and is attended by new challenges in performance capture, mastering and, rendering—all of which stem from the need to maintain a musically balanced listening experience that can adapt to a constantly changing listener position. We present our approach through the creation of an immersive music experience which is deployed for evaluation on two different kinds of audio displays: one with binaural rendering to headphones, and the other that renders to a hybrid loudspeaker system comprising our Satsphere (a large dome with a total of 157 speakers aggregated into 31 channels) for far field audio, and our set of five 12-channel spherical speakers (called Audiodice) for near field audio. The collected data is composed of 64+ audio channel recordings of the Orchestre Symphonique de Montréal conducted by Kent Nagano and a 3D model of the Maison Symphonique de Montréal. This data is described in detail below, and made available with a non-commercial Creative Commons licence.

1. INTRODUCTION

Mainstream uses of game engines and related technological advancements in authoring and rendering 3D object audio scenes have paved the way for a new paradigm in music experience, and by extension, music creation. Using these novel technologies, music can be represented as a spatial arrangement of sound source objects in a virtual 3D audio scene in which a virtual listener is located. The quality of the listening experience, or *listening perspective* as we call it, is determined by the position and orientation, or *6DoF pose* (Degrees of Freedom), of the virtual listener with respect to the surrounding sound source objects in the

audio scene. Moving the listener and/or sources within the audio scene yields a change to the listening perspective, and thus allows a listener to focus or *zoom* his/her listening attention on different features of the music. This activity changes the relative intensities among source sounds that comprise a piece of music and thus can eliminate auditory masking effects [1], allowing for otherwise inaccessible features of the music to be revealed. Simply put, the ability to navigate one’s listening perspective *within* a musical structure can translate to the ability to hear more, especially when listening to music of greater timbral and/or compositional complexity. Interestingly enough, our informal experiences with the public suggest that this ability tends to benefit trained and untrained listeners alike.

In this paper we describe our novel approach to ensemble recording, mastering, and music listening. What sets our approach apart from traditional methods is the ability to provide a plurality of listening perspectives within the recording space. While microphone placement is key in all approaches, our underlying strategy greatly differs. In traditional classical recording the microphones are strategically placed within the recording space to constitute a *single* listening perspective. Remixing the captured audio streams to constitute other listening perspectives is ineffective because the originally targeted listening perspective is “baked in” to the streams. Conversely, in our approach, a comparatively greater number of microphones is strategically deployed and distributed to capture *zones* of musical interest within the recording space. Subsequently, the set of captured audio streams can be blended to create unique listening perspectives that correspond to *locations* within the physical recording space. Using this technique, audio renderers allow a user to dynamically transition, or *navigate*, his or her listening perspective throughout the captured recording space. In the following discussion we will present our approach and corresponding end-to-end pipeline, *from instrument to ear drum*, which comprises capture, authoring, and rendering stages.

This paper provides a background about sound field capture (Section 2) and discusses our 6DoF capture strategy in a large-scale symphonic music deployment (Section 3). We describe the dataset and how it is distributed for future research (Section 4). Finally, we demonstrate the use of the dataset for prototyping immersive experiences involving live navigation within the captured sound field (Sec-

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tion 5). We conclude with a discussion of our results and enumerate our work’s future directions (Section 6).

2. BACKGROUND

Human beings moving in space rely on hearing cues that contribute to a spatial understanding and appreciation of our surrounding sound field and space. The simulation of this primal sensation imposes many challenges regarding sound capture and reproduction. One of these challenges is the ability to reproduce navigation in an audio scene along 6 degrees of freedom (6 DoF), i.e. lateral, height and side rotations with translation along the 3 Cartesian axes.

According to Zhang *et al.* [2] spatial audio capture is divided into two main families: binaural capture and sound field capture. Binaural capture, by definition, provides a realistic stereo image in terms of sound depth but suffers from several major problems:

- the captured binaural signal does not allow navigation in the audio scene (0 DoF). Indeed, each microphone corresponds to one ear, not allowing different orientation afterwards when listening.
- the natural filter imposed by the shape of the listener’s head and ears contribute significantly to the perception of sound localization. As a result, one must be able to measure these coefficients for each listener [2] if one wants to provide a faithful spatial listening.

Sound field capture using 3D microphones allows sound to be recorded in all directions simultaneously, offering three additional degrees of freedom: lateral, vertical, and side rotation. While this capture method allows the sound field to be captured as a whole, sound sources are localized without being differentiated into independent audio channels. There is no known method today to infer the perspective of a sound scene from a single surround capture, but from another position in space. This is mainly due to the difficulty of isolating the sounds constituting the sound scene, their position, as well as the varying acoustics of complex geometry of the environment [3].

The use of 3D microphone arrays is still quite marginal and is gradually addressing the problems imposed by 6 DoF navigation. For example, [4] improves the performance of sound field capture by reducing the number of microphones needed for audio capture to follow a mobile sound source, such as a teleconference speaker [5]. This research emphasizes the accurate capture of a 2D shot by focusing primarily on the capture of mobile sound sources.

For the production of audio content in Virtual Reality, an English team evaluated the use of several microphone matrix configurations (3 and 6 DoF), with the objective of producing a binaural rendering synchronized with immersive video navigation [6, 7]. More recently, the company ZYLIA¹ has experimented with sound field capture using a 3D microphone array, with the aim of producing a 6-DoF navigation system [8]. This approach

¹ <http://www.zylia.co> (accessed Dec. 2020)

Figure 1. Microphone placement map for room capture

is based on a regular disposition of microphones in the space. Our approach provides more extensive “near-field” navigation where musician-specific locations are captured and provides independent gain control of acoustic (room microphones) and source (stage microphones) energy for wet/dry balancing.

Applications making use of acoustic space modelling using in situ measurements do not usually provide a 6 DoF navigation experience of the simulated space [9]. However, just like the shape and characteristics of sound sources, the reverberation effects of places are determining factors in the final sound effect perceived by the listener [10].

3. 6 DOF CAPTURE

While a conventional stereo master is created for a single listening perspective, a 6DoF master must accommodate a plurality of unique potential listening perspectives that could be rendered for a listener. The captured audio scene

consists of two basic types of sound sources: instrumental and reverberant. The main challenge is to capture a maximum amount of local sonic detail at data rates that can be rendered afterwards in real-time. The microphone set density, types and placement among the instruments or within the concert hall address this challenge.

To capture reverberation in the hall, we deploy 23 microphones, including the main rig, which is composed of three microphones arranged in a Decca tree [11]. These microphones are symmetrically positioned along the length of the venue. All are suspended from the ceiling at increasing heights from front to back. Most of the microphones are omnidirectional with a few exceptions. Room microphone detail is provided in Table 2, while on-stage microphone placement for instrumental capture is illustrated by Fig. 1. Most of the choices for microphone directivity patterns are inspired from state-of-the-art aspects of recording acoustic classic music [12].

3.1 Recording space

The Maison Symphonique de Montreal² is the performance venue of the Orchestre Symphonique de Montréal and its conductor, Maestro Kent Nagano. Built in 2011, it was designed by Diamond Schmitt Architects and Ædifica with lead acoustician Bob Essert. The tall and narrow room, based on a traditional shoebox design, is a composition of convex curves of varying size, spreading out the sound and creating a warm, lush timbre. “The walls are large, gently convex panels, designed to spread the sound throughout the hall, to create an intense and immersive sound, drawing the audience into the performance. The scale and curvature of the panels are carefully tailored to refine the frequency spectrum, and therefore the timbre of the sound.”³ The auditorium meets noise criterion N1, in which the background noise level in the hall is not audible to the human ear. The recording control room is close to the stage on the left.

For our recordings, the Orchestre Symphonique de Montréal, conducted by Maestro Kent Nagano, was performing Beethoven’s 6th Symphony (Pastorale) on February 18th 2020 with rehearsals on February 16th and 17th. The orchestra is arranged in an antiphonal setup, so the first violins are on the left of the conductor, with the second violins on his right. This is the main difference from the more common Stokowski Shift seating arrangement [13].

3.2 Capture Description

The equipment used for the recording is based on a MADI backbone and Merging Technologies Pyramix DAW. The recording session running on two redundant Window laptops is set @ 96kHz / 24 bits, 62 discrete sources are recorded along with a guide stereo mixdown. All microphone preamps are remote-controlled from the recording booth, so they can be placed close to the sources to which

²<https://www.osm.ca/en/the-hall/>, accessed in March 2021.

³Essert, B. (2011) Acoustics Design – La Maison Symphonique, Montreal in <https://www.soundspacevision.com/>, accessed Feb. 2021.

they are connected. The microphones are divided in two groups. Group 1 includes all the point source inputs that are placed on stage, recording local instruments. Group 2 represents the room sources; all microphones are suspended from the ceiling. As the capture took place during a live performance in a packed venue for Maestro Kent Nagano’s final concert with the Orchestre Symphonique de Montréal (OSM), we needed to integrate the following constraints:

- No microphone stands or running cables in the space where the audience was seated.
- All room microphones had to be suspended from the ceiling.
- A limited number of cable-pass-thru holes in the ceiling that thus determined microphone positions.
- Limited time to suspend microphones and make adjustments.
- A one-take session, in which a single performance was captured, removing the option to edit in post-production.

The 38 microphones on stage capture isolated instruments or groups of instruments. They are mounted on microphone stands and connected to the microphone preamps through multi-pair cables. Original files are captured as a multi-channel wav file with 96kHz sample rate and 24 bit depth. More details are provided by Table 1 and microphone placement on the stage is illustrated by Fig. 2. In the tables, X, Y and Z are expressed in meters, the origin is located at the feet of the conductor, X being directed toward its right (left-right axis), Y toward its front (front-back axis), and Z towards its top (vertical axis).

4. DATASET

As part of our work, we have created a dataset of high quality live recordings of Beethoven’s 6th Symphony performed by the OSM. We used these recordings to drive our navigable virtual model of the symphony hall described in Section 5. The dataset consists of 62 wav files, one for each microphone placed in the hall. Each file has the same duration, containing a single audio channel that was captured at a specified location in the hall during a live performance of the symphony. The dataset also includes a 3D model of the Maison Symphonique de Montreal, containing a simple representation of the performance space, as well as both groups of microphones deployed in the hall and on stage respectively.

We have made the complete dataset freely available for download at https://archive.org/details/savr_audio_dataset in the hopes that others will be able to use it for further audio research. These recordings are licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution Non-Commercial ShareAlike 4.0 International License.

Group	#	label	Microphone	Preamp	X	Y	Z	Filename	Directivity
1st violin	24	V1.1	Neumann KM 143	Grace Design m108 #4	-1.43	1.08	1.5	024_V1.1	cardioid
	25	V1.2	Neumann KM 140	Grace Design m108 #4	-2.91	1.36	1.5	025_V1.2	cardioid
	26	V1.3	Schoeps CMC621	Grace Design m108 #4	-4.26	1.49	1.5	026_V1.3	between omni and cardioid
	27	V1.4	Schoeps CMC621	Grace Design m108 #4	-5.56	1.74	1.5	027_V1.4	between omni and cardioid
	28	V1.5	Neumann KM 140	Grace Design m108 #4	-7.05	2.06	1.5	028_V1.5	cardioid
2nd violin	29	V2.1	Neuman KM 143	Grace Design m108 #4	1.2	1.04	1.5	029_V2.1	between omni and cardioid
	30	V2.2	Neuman KM 140	Grace Design m108 #4	2.74	1.32	1.5	030_V2.2	cardioid
	31	V2.3	Neuman KM 140	Grace Design m108 #4	3.85	1.53	1.5	031_V2.3	cardioid
	32	V2.4	Neuman KM 140	RME Octamic XTC #1	5.39	1.88	1.5	032_V2.4	cardioid
	33	V2.5	Neuman KM 140	RME Octamic XTC #1	6.86	2.26	1.5	033_V2.5	cardioid
Violas	34	Va.1	Sennheiser MKH 8040	RME Octamic XTC #1	0.64	2.3	1.5	034_Va.1	cardioid
	35	Va.2	Sennheiser MKH 8040	RME Octamic XTC #1	2.35	3.27	1.5	035_Va.2	cardioid
	36	Va.3	Schoeps CMC622	RME Octamic XTC #1	0.91	4.23	1.5	036_Va.3	between omni and cardioid
	37	Va.4	Schoeps CMC622	RME Octamic XTC #1	2.83	4.72	1.5	037_Va.4	between omni and cardioid
	38	Va.5	Neuman KM 140	RME Octamic XTC #1	1.26	5.59	1.5	038_Va.5	cardioid
Cellos	39	Vc.1	Coles 4038	RME Octamic XTC #1	-0.84	2.35	0.8	039_Vc.1	figure eight
	40	Vc.2	Sennheiser MKH 800	Grace Design m108 #5	-2.54	2.82	0.8	040_Vc.2	cardioid
	41	Vc.3	Sennheiser MKH 800	Grace Design m108 #5	-0.93	4.09	0.8	041_Vc.3	cardioid
	42	Vc.4	Sennheiser MKH 800	Grace Design m108 #5	-2.86	4.67	0.8	042_Vc.4	cardioid
	43	Vc.5	Sennheiser MKH 800	Grace Design m108 #5	-1.08	5.55	0.8	043_Vc.5	cardioid
Basses	44	Vb.1	Coles 4038	Grace Design m108 #5	-5.38	5.42	0.8	044_Vb.1	figure eight
	45	Vb.2	Neumann TLM 103	Grace Design m108 #5	-6.98	3.97	0.8	045_Vb.2	cardioid
	46	Vb.3	Sennheiser MK 8020	Grace Design m108 #5	-7.85	5.52	0.8	046_Vb.3	omni
Woodwinds	47	Fl.2	Neumann KM 84	Grace Design m108 #5	-1.49	6.93	1.3	047_Fl.2	cardioid
	48	Fl.1	Neumann KM 84	RME Octamic XTC #2	-0.68	6.99	1.3	048_Fl.1	cardioid
Oboes	49	Ob.1	Neumann KM 84	RME Octamic XTC #2	0.26	6.91	1.3	049_Ob.1	cardioid
	50	Ob.2	Neumann KM 84	RME Octamic XTC #2	1.14	6.88	1.3	050_Ob.2	cardioid
Clarinets	51	Kl.2	Neumann KM 84	RME Octamic XTC #2	-1.55	8.26	0.8	051_Clar.2	cardioid
	52	Kl.1	Neumann KM 140	RME Octamic XTC #2	-0.79	8.317	0.8	052_Clar.1	cardioid
Bassoons	53	Fg.1	Neumann KM 85	RME Octamic XTC #2	0.87	8.439	1	053_Bsn.1	cardioid
	54	Fg.2	Neumann KM 140	RME Octamic XTC #2	1.736	8.167	1	054_Bsn.2	cardioid
Horns	55	Horn.1	Neumann KM 84	RME Octamic XTC #2	-4.34	8.85	0.8	055_Hrn.1	cardioid
	56	Horn.2	Neumann KM 84	Millennia HV-3R	-5.11	8.32	0.8	056_Hrn.2	cardioid
Trumpets	57	Tpt.1	AEA R84	Millennia HV-3R	2.47	10.65	1	057_Trp.1	figure eight
	58	Tpt.2	AEA R84	Millennia HV-3R	3.65	10.36	1	058_Trp.2	figure eight
Trombones	59	Tbn.1	Neumann TLM 67	Millennia HV-3R	4.92	9.84	1	059_Tbn.1	cardioid
	60	Tbn.2	Neumann TLM 67	Millennia HV-3R	6.03	8.89	1	060_Tbn.2	cardioid
Timpani	61	Tim.1	AKG c414	Millennia HV-3R	-0.51	11.13	1.9	061_Timb.1	cardioid
	62	Tim.2	AKG c414	Millennia HV-3R	0.4	11.19	1.9	062_Timb.2	cardioid

Table 1. Specification of microphones used for the audio capture of instruments.

5. NAVIGATION IN THE ORCHESTRA

5.1 Concepts and Strategies

The ability to navigate a listening perspective *anywhere* within a virtual audio scene is at the core of our approach, and greatly differs from methods used in conventional recording and mastering, which seeks to provide one *single* pre-determined listening perspective.

Our work combines theoretical and empirical approaches to the authoring and rendering of navigable symphonic music listening experiences. This includes a musical orientation, tempered by years of first-hand experience in orchestral sound recording, mastering and music composition. In working with the presented orchestral music, the goal has been to create a navigable music scene with the following essential properties:

1. The scene is balanced among captured channels from any listening position.
2. The scene provides a high degree of differentiation and detail when zoomed on particular instrument zones.
3. The scene provides a natural sounding stereo image whose width changes appropriately with distance.
4. The scene provides, at any distance, a natural sound-balance of reverberant and instrumental sound sources.

Figure 2. Microphone placement map for instrument capture.

#	label	Microphone	Preamp	Hole#	X	Y	Z	Height (m)	Filename	Directivity
1	Main L	DPA 4006	Grace Design m108 #1	23	-1	0.04	4	4.00	001_L	omni
2	Main R	DPA 4006	Grace Design m108 #1	22	1	0.04	4	4.00	002_R	omni
3	Main C	DPA 4006	Grace Design m108 #1	19/18	0	1.37	3.45	3.75	003_C	omni
4	Side L	Sennheiser MKH8020	Grace Design m108 #1	23	-5.9	0.04	2.2	2.23	004_Side	omni
5	Side R	Sennheiser MKH8020	Grace Design m108 #1	22	5.9	0.04	2.1	2.10	005_Side	omni
6	AB L	DPA 4006	Grace Design m108 #1	28	-1	-4.44	6.17	6.17	006_AB	omni
7	AB R	DPA 4006	Grace Design m108 #1	27	1	-4.44	6.17	6.17	007_AB	omni
8	Room L	Sennheiser MKH8020	Grace Design m108 #1	34	-1.3	-8.96	7	7.00	008_Room	omni
9	Room R	Sennheiser MKH8020	Grace Design m108 #2	33	1.3	-8.96	7	7.00	009_Room	omni
10	Room WL	DPA 4006	Grace Design m108 #2	36	-5.9	-8.96	5	5.00	010_Room_W	omni
11	Room WR	DPA 4006	Grace Design m108 #2	31	5.9	-8.96	5	5.00	011_Room_W	omni
12	Salle 1L	Schoeps CMC641	Grace Design m108 #2	34	-1.6	-8.96	7	7.00	012_Salle1	hypercardioid
13	Salle 1R	Schoeps CMC641	Grace Design m108 #2	33	1.6	-8.96	7	7.00	013_Salle1	hypercardioid
14	Salle 2L	Sennheiser MKH8020	Grace Design m108 #2	47	3.6	-14.11	5	5.00	014_Salle2	omni
15	Salle 2R	Sennheiser MKH8020	Grace Design m108 #2	44	-3.76	-14.11	5	5.00	015_Salle2	omni
16	Salle 3L	Sennheiser MKH8020	Grace Design m108 #2	54	-5.88	-18.04	5	5.00	016_Salle3	omni
17	Salle 3R	Sennheiser MKH8020	Grace Design m108 #3	49	5.88	-18.04	5	5.00	017_Salle3	omni
18	Salle 4L	Schoeps CMC641	Grace Design m108 #3	54	-6	-22.27	6	6.00	018_Salle4	hypercardioid
19	Salle 4 R	Schoeps CMC641	Grace Design m108 #3	49	6	-22.27	6	6.00	019_Salle4	hypercardioid
20	Balc 1L	Sennheiser MKH8020	Grace Design m108 #3	48	-5.89	-14.11	5	6.60	020_BalcL	omni
21	Balc 2L	Sennheiser MKH8020	Grace Design m108 #3	54	-6.52	-18.04	6.6	6.60	021_BalcL	omni
22	Balc 1R	Sennheiser MKH8020	Grace Design m108 #3	43	6.01	-14.11	5	6.60	022_BalcR	omni
23	Balc 2R	Sennheiser MKH8020	Grace Design m108 #3	49	6.52	-18.04	6.6	6.60	y023_BalcR	omni

Table 2. Specification of microphones used for the audio room capture.

The biggest challenge has been to combine and balance *all* the above in *one single* audio scene. Ideally, at one moment, the listening perspective can be navigated to a central location in say, the 7th row, in order to deliver a well-blended listening experience akin to those targeted by conventional concert recordings. Then at another moment, the perspective can be smoothly navigated to a different location *within* the orchestra to reveal fine sonic detail among the woodwinds. Via strategic capture and rendering techniques, we address the challenges that accompany listening perspective navigation.

5.2 Mixing by Arrangement

Our virtual audio scene is a collection of reverberant and instrumental sound sources, each emitting audio that was captured by a particular microphone. As shown earlier, twenty-eight microphones were suspended from the ceiling to capture reverberation in the concert hall shown in Fig. 1, while thirty-four microphones were positioned on the stage to capture the direct instrumental sounds shown in Fig. 2. The location of each source in the 3D audio scene corresponds to the location of a specific microphone in the real concert hall. Thus, the arrangement of the sound sources in the virtual scene *exactly* corresponds to the microphone arrangement in the recording session as shown in Fig. 3. The quality of the output mix is determined by the virtual listener’s position and angle, or 6DoF pose, in the virtual audio scene, with respect to all the scene’s sound sources.

5.3 Rendering the Listening Perspective

The listening perspective consists of a weighted sum of processed outputs from all the scene’s audio sources. The processing of each audio source is based on the difference between that source’s 6DoF pose and the 6DoF pose of the listener. Any time a listener or source moves, the perspective is updated, and low level parameters are computed (azimuth, elevation, gain, delay and spread) based on the following geometrical information: i) The distance between

 Figure 3. Virtual audio sources positioned *one to one* according to the microphone placement map

the listener and the source, ii) The angular position of the listener relative to the source, and iii) The incidence of the listener relative to the source.

Using these relations, we dynamically compute values for each source mixing parameter below: i) Attenuation, using distance and incidence, ii) Near Field Processing, using distance, iii) Filtering using distance and incidence, iv) Spread using distance, and v) Delay or *Doppler* using distance.

Our renderer offers the ability to describe distance/value functions for these parameters, thus allowing us to define custom attenuation-by-distance curves, etc. In addition to the dynamic parameters above, the following static mixing parameters can be adjusted independently for each source: i) Attenuation Trim (db), ii) Doppler Effect (percent), iii) Near Field Effect (percent), and iv) Near Field Radius (meters)

5.4 6DoF Mastering

Unlike a conventional non-navigable master, which is created for a single listening perspective, a 6DoF master must accommodate a plurality of different listening perspectives as shown in Fig. 5. Whereas a conventional master, such

Figure 4. Source audio processing based on relative distances and incidences to listener

Figure 5. Mastering to accommodate a plurality of listening perspectives

as stereo or surround, is a rendered piece of audio content, the 6DoF master is a *renderable* 3D virtual audio scene. To a certain extent, our workflow resembles a game development environment. In order to create navigable audio scenes, we have developed custom workflows that help us achieve an optimized balance of the essential properties mentioned earlier. To achieve this balance, our workflow allows us to carefully adjust or *tune* both dynamic and static parameters, shown above, for all the scene’s reverberant and instrumental sound sources.

Except for the Doppler/delay parameters, which we minimize for musical applications, our parameter adjustments determine the following attributes of the mix:

1. *Wet to Dry* Ratio, which in our case, refers to the balance between reverberant sources and instrumental sources.
2. Near Field Dynamics [14], that determine the quality and amount of *sonic zoom* that occurs when listening close to instrumental sources.
3. Spatial Localization Intensity, the degree to which, a given source is perceived to originate from a singular location in the space surrounding the listener.

We begin the mastering process by pre-establishing, in musical terms, overall ranges for the attributes above as

the perspective is moved variously throughout the entire audio scene. We then go about adjusting the mixing parameters in order to achieve a reasonable balance of essential properties across a wide range of potential listening perspective locations. Furthermore, we refer to this activity as *tuning the audio scene*. Based on the type of source sound, reverberant or instrumental, a source’s mixing parameter values will be tuned to augment or reduce the degrees of spatial localization, near-field effect, attenuation by distance, etc. To make this authoring process easier and more efficient, we have developed mixing operations such as grouping, for subsets of reverberant sources, and for instrumental sources. In addition to parameter changes, these groups also allow us to mute and offset the gains of their respective sources, as we tune our mixes.

In conventional mastering, the final outcome is the result of iterations of adjustment and evaluation on different loudspeaker configurations. The same holds true for our 6DoF mastering process. To our great surprise, the resulting 6DoF master audio scene yielded the same high-quality music experience when rendered for stereo headphones, and for the 31 channel Satsphere dome, alike. No “re-tuning” of the audio scene was required when changing among output rendering formats, even when they differed greatly. Even more surprising, when rendering on the hybrid audio system combining the Satsphere and five Audiodice⁴ spherical speakers, for far and near field display respectively, the audio scene still did not require adjustment⁵.

To date, we have applied our workflow to create unique 6DoF masters for three different symphonic works: Beethoven’s Pastoral, Beethoven’s Seventh, and Pascal Dusapin’s “Wave”. In the process, we have observed that reusing an audio scene with parameters adjusted for one piece of music, such as the Beethoven Pastoral, when rendering a different work, such as the Dusapin’s “Wave”, yielded poorer listening experiences in terms of the essential properties mentioned earlier. As with conventional masters, if not even more so, it would appear that 6DoF masters need to be uniquely crafted to each piece, based on possible variations among sound sources locations and specific nature of the compositions.

5.5 Platform

5.5.1 Rendering

The rendering stage of our pipeline shown in Fig. 6 incorporates both the Unity and SuperCollider environments, each of which has been extended to render the music scene in tandem⁶. Running in SuperCollider, the SATIE [15] library, developed by the SAT Metalab, provides an extremely efficient realtime dynamic audio processing environment, and offers a wide range of extendable output format configurations. The inputs to SATIE consist of raw au-

⁴ See the Audiodice prototype building at <https://vimeo.com/519938720>. Accessed March 2021.

⁵ See our demonstration video at <https://vimeo.com/519940468>. Accessed March 2021.

⁶ The code repository is published under the GPL licence and is available here : <https://gitlab.com/sat-metalab/6dmastering4savr>

Figure 6. Distributed authoring and rendering pipeline

Figure 7. Authoring tools for 6DoF mastering

dio streams and asynchronous rendering messages. SATIE outputs rendered audio streams for one or more listeners, in one or more audio output formats, such as binaural stereo, high-order ambisonics, or the custom 31-channel Satsphere Dome format. SATIE can also simultaneously render near and far field perspectives, as separate audio output streams, which can be useful when using hybrid audio displays [16].

In our pipeline, SATIE functions as an audio processor, computing a node-based DSP graph of sources and syncs. Input messages to SATIE mainly comprise source-specific lists of DSP update parameters for gain, delay and filtering. The messages are sent asynchronously over IP by a library running in the Unity Environment called *Satie4Unity*, also developed by the SAT Metalab. *Satie4Unity* provides control for update message density, which we typically limit to no more than 10 to 20 times per second, per source node. In SATIE, the received update message parameters are smoothed.

The input to *Satie4Unity* is the 3D audio scene graph, or “6DoF master” referred to above, which contains one or more listeners and a spatial arrangement of reverberation and instrumental source objects. Basically, *Satie4Unity* converts changes to 3D source and listener geometry into batches of source-listener DSP parameter updates, which are transmitted as OSC messages to SATIE.

5.5.2 Authoring

Satie4Unity also extends Unity’s native authoring UI, and thus allows us to build tools that integrate existing UI features for editing curves or adjusting parameters, shown in Fig. 7. As our Authoring/Rendering pipeline runs in real-time, these tools serve our requirement to instantly hear adjustments we make to the audio scene during the mastering process.

6. DISCUSSION AND FUTURE WORKS

The approach we describe here provides general guidelines for building navigable listening experiences, and more particularly about the working pipeline strategy. The division of the capture in *zones* (stage vs. hall) has provided expected results in terms of 6DoF mastering flexibility when fine-tuning the 6DoF mastering for different recorded pieces. Additionally, our strategy takes advantage of conventional capturing equipment, techniques and expertise, permitting for the use of particular microphones with specific patterns and preamps.

Our work to date has led us to consider several improvements and promising new deployments to investigate :

1. Use of ambisonic microphones to capture reverberation in the acoustic space. Ambisonic microphones will provide extra directionality and may improve subtle variations in reverberation
2. Add a rendering effect to enhance the degree of spatial encompassment at different distances from a cluster of instrumental source sounds.
3. Use of *outside in* microphone arrays to capture and then render a single source from multiple surrounding angles.
4. Extension of near field rendering techniques for sources captured by *outside in* microphone arrays, and rendered for the Audiodice spherical audio display system.
5. Implementation of geometry-based acoustic modelling for live navigable reverberation rendering with live ray tracing [17].
6. The use of binaural recordings, captured by an itinerant listener during the recording session, for comparative evaluations of rendered listening experiences.
7. Extension of the dataset with directional impulse responses measures of the Maison Symphonique de Montréal

7. CONCLUSION

Indeed, the ability to navigate complex forms of music, such as symphonic works, modern or otherwise, can yield a particularly compelling listening experience in terms of one’s ability to recognize and differentiate timbral and structural elements in the music. We are convinced that our efforts have been effective in developing a pipeline that can deliver navigable music listening experiences of high musical quality. We have furthered our understanding of microphone deployment density and placement. In the authoring of the three previously mentioned 6DoF masters, we have addressed the need to potentially render *all* listening perspectives, and created workflows with musically prioritized steps and operations to simplify the task and improve the result. Finally, we have been able to evaluate the effectiveness of music scene organization in terms of

reverberation and instrumental sources. While we are excited by the results we obtained, we recognize that there is much work still to be done, including potential to extend the captured navigable space to improve listening quality at elevated locations in the audio scene. Finally, through our work with real-time interactive experience rendering on a large symphonic scale, we have achieved a difficult balance between data density and musical experience quality.

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8. REFERENCES

- [1] S. McAdams and A. Bregman, "Hearing musical streams," *Computer Music Journal*, vol. 3, no. 4, pp. 26–60, 1979. [Online]. Available: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/4617866>
- [2] W. Zhang, P. N. Samarasinghe, H. Chen, and T. D. Abhayapala, "Surround by sound: A review of spatial audio recording and reproduction," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 7, no. 5, 2017. [Online]. Available: <http://www.mdpi.com/2076-3417/7/5/532>
- [3] J.-H. Wang, A. Qu, T. R. Langlois, and D. L. James, "Toward wave-based sound synthesis for computer animation," *ACM Trans. Graph.*, vol. 37, no. 4, pp. 109:1–109:16, Jul. 2018. [Online]. Available: <http://doi.acm.org/10.1145/3197517.3201318>
- [4] P. Samarasinghe, T. Abhayapala, and M. Poletti, "Wavefield analysis over large areas using distributed higher order microphones," *IEEE/ACM Transactions on Audio, Speech, and Language Processing*, vol. 22, no. 3, pp. 647–658, March 2014.
- [5] H. F. Silverman, W. R. Patterson, and J. L. Flanagan, "The huge microphone array," *IEEE Concurrency*, vol. 6, no. 4, pp. 36–46, Oct 1998.
- [6] D. Rivas Méndez, C. Armstrong, J. Stubbs, M. Stiles, and G. Kearney, "Practical recording techniques for music production with six-degrees of freedom virtual reality," in *Audio Engineering Society Convention 145*, Oct 2018. [Online]. Available: <http://www.aes.org/e-lib/browse.cfm?elib=19729>
- [7] H. Riaz, M. Stiles, C. Armstrong, A. Chadwick, H. Lee, and G. Kearney, "Multichannel microphone array recording for popular music production in virtual reality," *Audio Engineering Society, Convention e-Brief*, 10 2017.
- [8] E. Patricio, A. Ruminski, A. Kuklasinski, L. Januszkiewicz, and T. Zernicki, "Toward six degrees of freedom audio recording and playback using multiple ambisonics sound fields," in *Audio Engineering Society Convention 146*, Mar 2019. [Online]. Available: <http://www.aes.org/e-lib/browse.cfm?elib=20274>
- [9] S. Tervo and A. Politis, "Direction of arrival estimation of reflections from room impulse responses using a spherical microphone array," *IEEE/ACM Transactions on Audio, Speech and Language Processing (TASLP)*, vol. 23, no. 10, pp. 1539–1551, 2015.
- [10] B. F. G. Katz and D. Poirier-Quinot, "Archéologie acoustique par reconstruction virtuelle pour l'analyse in situ," *Culture et recherche*, no. 141, pp. 25–26, Sep. 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-02940162>
- [11] J. Borwick, *Sound Recording Practice*, T. Tryggvason, Ed. London: Oxford University Press, 1976.
- [12] C. Haigh, J. Dunkerley, and M. Rogers, *Classical Recording: A Practical Guide in the Decca Tradition (1st ed.)*. London: Focal Press, Oct. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780429316852>.
- [13] J. Meyer, *Seating Arrangement in the Concert Hall*. New York, NY: Springer New York, 2009, pp. 263–346. [Online]. Available: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-0-387-09517-2_7
- [14] D. R. Moore and A. J. King, "Auditory perception: The near and far of sound localization," *Current Biology*, vol. 9, no. 10, pp. R361 – R363, 1999. [Online]. Available: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0960982299802279>
- [15] N. Bouillot, M. . Seta, Émile Ouellet-Delorme, Z. Settel, and E. Durand, "Rendering of heterogeneous spatial audio scenes," in *Proceedings of the 17th Linux Audio Conference (LAC-19)*, Mar. 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://gitlab.com/sat-metalab/metalabbib/raw/master/papers/2019bouillot2.pdf?inline=false>
- [16] Z. Settel, P. Otto, M. . Seta, and N. Bouillot, "Dual rendering of virtual audio scenes for far-field surround multi-channel and near-field binaural audio displays," in *16th Biennial Symposium on Arts and Technology*, Ammerman Center for Arts and Technology at Connecticut College, New London, Feb. 2018, 5 pages. [Online]. Available: <https://gitlab.com/sat-metalab/metalabbib/raw/master/papers/2018settel.pdf?inline=false>
- [17] Émile Ouellet-Delorme, H. Venkatesan, E. Durand, and N. Bouillot, "Live ray tracing and auralization of 3d audio scene with vaRays (submitted)," in *18th Sound and Music Computing Conference (SMC)*, 2021.